

Protocol for Adaptive Emission Reduction Approach (AERA) simulations

December 22nd 2022

Thomas Frölicher, Jens Terhaar, Fortunat Joos, Yona Silvy

Climate and Environmental Physics and Oeschger Centre for Climate Change Research, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland; thomas.froelicher@unibe.ch, jens.terhaar@unibe.ch, fortunat.joos@unibe.ch, yona.silvy@unibe.ch

Documents and updates are available online: <https://github.com/Jete90/AERA>

Cite this document as:

Frölicher, T.L., J. Terhaar, F. Joos, Y. Silvy (2022). Protocol for Adaptive Emission Reduction Approach (AERA) simulations (v2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7473133>

1. General idea

The adaptive emission reduction approach (AERA) aims to quantify CO₂ forcing equivalent (CO₂-fe) emission reductions every five years following the stocktake mechanism implemented in the Paris Agreement (Terhaar et al. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01537-9>). Every five years, the AERA estimates the necessary emission reductions for a chosen temperature target only based on observations or simulations of the past annual global mean surface temperatures (GMST) or global mean surface air temperature (GSAT), past CO₂ emissions, and radiative forcing from non-CO₂ forcing agents. The radiative forcing from non-CO₂ forcing agents is used to calculate CO₂-fe emissions, i.e., the amount of CO₂ emissions over time that would lead to the observed or simulated radiative forcing time series.

The AERA consists of three main steps: (1) determining the past anthropogenic warming and hence the remaining warming allowed, (2) estimating the remaining CO₂-fe emission budget (REB), and (3) proposing a future CO₂-fe curve.

First, the anthropogenic warming is calculated from observed or simulated GMST or GSAT time-series using a predefined fitting method, in order to filter out internally-driven temperature changes. In the intercomparison modelling exercise proposed here, a simple 31-year running mean is applied to simulated global near-surface air temperature.

Second, the REB of CO₂-fe emissions that can still be emitted before the target temperature will be reached is estimated using the transient climate response to cumulative emissions (TCRE) up to the current year, defined as the ratio of past warming and past cumulative CO₂-fe emissions. The REB is estimated as the remaining warming until the temperature target is reached divided by TCRE. Here, we rely on the linear relationship between cumulative CO₂-fe emissions and warming over the past and the near-future.

When quantified, the REB of CO₂-fe emissions is distributed over the future years in a third step using a cubic polynomial function. Many possible CO₂-fe emission curves for the future may exist for one specific REB with different economic and political assumptions. For simplicity, we chose the parameters of the cubic function by minimizing the curvature, i.e., the sum of the absolute annual rates of change of the slope of the CO₂-fe emission curve (2nd derivative). Thereby, we assume that relatively small changes over a longer time starting now, like in the emission pathways of the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways, are more likely to be implemented than a strong and abrupt reduction in CO₂-fe emission in the future. It may happen that the curve with the smallest curvature has positive emissions that are later compensated by negative emissions, which would effectively result in a temporary temperature overshoot. To avoid such an overshoot, we also minimized exceedance emissions, i.e., negative emissions if the REB is still positive or positive emissions if the REB is negative. A negative REB may, nevertheless, still occur if the anthropogenic warming or the TCRE turns out to be larger than estimated in the previous stocktakes.

The successive application of the AERA every five years adjusts the future CO₂-fe emission curve each time based on the most up-to-date and best observations or simulations of GSAT and CO₂-fe emissions. If the anthropogenic

warming will turn out to be different than anticipated by the time of the next stocktake, the adaptive nature of the AERA will adjust future emissions successively.

The AERA has been tested intensively using the Bern3D EMIC in many different configurations (e.g. varying climate sensitivity, etc.) as a substitute for the real world, as well as with the fully coupled Earth system models GFDL ESM2M and CESM2.

2. Difference to prescribed scenarios

So far policymakers and scientists investigating climate change, its impacts and costs were presented with a limited number of socio-economic scenarios with assumptions of emissions or concentrations for the whole 21st century and sometimes beyond. By using different Earth system models, climate modelers then estimated the expected temperature increase for each scenario, yielding a best guess for the temperature for given emissions or concentration trajectories for several forcing agents. However, the estimated warming still has substantial uncertainties.

Instead of relying on socio-economical emissions scenarios, the AERA provides periodically updated CO₂-fe emissions time series for policymakers that will allow reaching a chosen temperature target. The often large uncertainty in climate projections is side-stepped by the adaptive approach: proposed emission trajectories are periodically adjusted based on the most up-to-date observations, and the temperature target will be reached in the end when following the proposed CO₂-fe emissions time series.

Moreover, policy makers now get the reductions in CO₂-fe emissions and can distribute these CO₂-fe emissions reductions across the number of forcing agents (CO₂, methane, ...) as it fits best at a given stocktake, leaving more freedom of choice and do not only get presented a limited number of scenarios. The split of emission reductions across different agents can be computed using the Global Warming Potential with a time horizon of 100 years (GWP₁₀₀), the metric of choice by the UNFCCC, e.g., in the Kyoto basket approach. In other words, the GWP₁₀₀ metric can be used to implement the proposed CO₂-fe emission reductions and no change in the UNFCCC regulations and the Paris Agreement are needed to implement the suggested CO₂-fe emissions reductions.

3. Reasoning for Earth system model simulations

The simulations with the Earth System Models (ESMs) have the following main purpose.

First, simulations should provide an estimate of emission pathways that are compatible with certain temperature targets such as 1.5°C and 2.0°C. This will allow assessing Earth System changes that are associated with the pathways to these targets. Surface ocean pH (i.e., acidity) projections, for example, have almost no uncertainty in concentration-driven ESM projections because changes in surface ocean pH follow closely the changes in the prescribed atmospheric CO₂ concentration in RCPs and SSPs. However, if all models reach the same temperature target with the AERA, atmospheric CO₂ trajectories in each model will differ and result in a wider range of surface ocean pH projections that yield a more realistic uncertainty of the ocean acidification associated with a certain temperature target (Terhaar, J, T. L. Frölicher, F. Joos, Ocean acidification in emission-driven temperature stabilization scenarios: the role of TCRE and non-CO₂ greenhouse gases, *Environmental Research Letters*, under review).

Second, the simulations with AERA will lead to near-stable GSAT. This will allow assessing the climatic impacts of different temperature targets (e.g., 1.5°C and 2°C) under stabilization. In the sixth Assessment Report differences in climate parameters for different GSAT were assessed by evaluating simulations where the target temperature was passed transiently and GSAT was not stabilizing at the temperature of interest. Arguably, the simulations with AERA will provide a better framework to assess the impacts associated with different climate targets.

Third, earlier studies investigating overshoot scenarios conducted either very idealized and unrealistic simulations or used climate models with reduced complexity. Whether Earth system changes from temporarily overshooting a certain temperature target (e.g., 1.5°C) are reversible is a key research gap identified in the IPCC Special Report on Global Warming of 1.5°C and the IPCC AR6 WGII report. The new AERA simulations with comprehensive fully coupled ESMs will help to close this research gap.

4. Simulation strategy

Here, we describe the implementation of the AERA in ESMs. The simulation setup can be divided in three parts, (A) the 'historical period' from 1850 to 2025, (B) the 'AERA period 1' starting in 2026 with the emission reductions implemented that were estimated by the AERA in 2025 and are re-evaluated by the AERA every 5 years, and (C) the 'AERA period 2' from 2100 to 2150 using the AERA to ensure that the temperature stabilizes (Fig. 1). The applied forcing during these three parts is described in detail below.

Fig. 1: Schematic of the three different AERA periods. The scheme shows idealized temperature time series for the 1.5°C (blue) and 2.0°C (orange) temperature targets and the three simulation periods.

A) Historical period (1850-2025)

A1) 1850-2014:

- i. Historical fossil fuel CO₂ emissions (CMIP6 protocol for emission driven scenarios)
- ii. Non-CO₂ forcing agent concentrations (CMIP6 protocol)
- iii. Land use and land cover change (CMIP6 protocol)

A2) 2015-2020:

- i. Historical fossil fuel CO₂ emissions (Global Carbon budget)
- ii. Non-CO₂ forcing agent concentrations (SSP1-2.6)
- iii. Land use and land cover change (SSP1-2.6)

A3) 2021-2025:

- i. Fossil fuel CO₂ emissions (NDC – Nationally determined contributions)
- ii. Non-CO₂ forcing agent concentrations (SSP1-2.6)
- iii. Land use and land cover change (SSP1-2.6)

B) AERA period 1 (2026-2100)

2026-2030:

- i. CO₂ emissions determined from the adaptive emissions reduction algorithm (AERA) in 2025
- ii. Non-CO₂ forcing agent concentrations (SSP1-2.6)
- iii. Land use and land cover change (SSP1-2.6)

2031-2035:

- i. CO₂ emissions determined from the adaptive emissions reduction algorithm (AERA) in 2030
- ii. Non-CO₂ forcing agent concentrations (SSP1-2.6)
- iii. Land use and land cover change (SSP1-2.6)

Repeating until 2100

C) AERA period 2 (2101-2150)

2101-2105:

- i. CO₂ emissions determined from the adaptive emissions reduction algorithm (AERA) in 2100
- ii. Non-CO₂ forcing agent concentrations (if possible: constant values from year 2100 under SSP1-2.6; if not possible: follow SSP1-2.6 extension)
- iii. Land use and land cover (if possible: constant values from year 2100 under SSP1-2.6; if not possible: follow SSP1-2.6 extension)

Repeating until 2150 or, if possible, longer (to be sure that the temperature is really stabilized and allowing analyzing the impacts under quasi-equilibrated GSAT).

Please use the land use area (area of pasture, croplands, urban, ...) from 2100 for all years afterwards with no further change in net area under use and keeping management practices as in 2100. Alternatively, use the extension of SSP1-2.6 for land use. Please use the same concentrations for non-CO₂ radiative agents as in 2100 if possible. If that is not possible, please use the extension of SSP1-2.6. Please contact us if none of the proposed solutions works for you.

Non-CO₂ forcing agents also include aerosols. Please note that the spatially resolved CO₂ emission input file for the ESM after 2014 needs to be prepared by yourself as the AERA 'only' provides a global, annual CO₂ emission number. To do so, please divide the spatially resolved, monthly CO₂ emission file from 2014 (the last one of the historical period) in each cell (x,y) and in each month (m) by the total annual CO₂ emissions in year 2014 and multiply it by the prescribed CO₂ emissions for the year you need it for (e.g. for year 2015). Here is an example for the year 2015:

$$E_{CO_2}^{2015}(x, y, m) = \frac{E_{CO_2}^{2015}(global)}{\sum_m \int E_{CO_2}^{2014}(x,y,m) dx dy} * E_{CO_2}^{2014}(x, y, m)$$

By doing so, we assume that the spatial and monthly distribution does not change. This assumption has negligible impacts on climate and the carbon cycle, due to the relatively fast transport of CO₂ in the atmosphere.

5. Relative and absolute temperature target

Following this strategy, each model will have a different anthropogenic warming in 2025 and hence a different remaining allowable warming until the respective temperature target, e.g., 1.5°C is reached. Therefore, the remaining warming can be calculated in the AERA with two options:

- Option 1 ('relative' temperature target): Here, the remaining warming is calculated in 2020 based on observations. Step one of the AERA gives an anthropogenic warming of 1.22°C in 2020 when applied to observations. Therefore, the remaining allowable warming is 0.28°C for the 1.5°C target, 0.78°C for the 2°C target and 1.78°C for the 3°C target. The AERA thus calculates the temperature target in each model based on the models anthropogenic warming in 2020 plus the remaining allowable warming in 2020 estimated from observations (Fig. 2). In other words, each model estimates the emission curve over the 21st century for the same remaining allowable warming.
- Option 2 ('absolute' temperature target): Here, the remaining warming is calculated in 2020 based on the ESM simulation output and does not account for observations. The anthropogenic warming in 2020 is calculated from the modeled change in GMST relative to 1850-1900 using the prescribed past radiative forcing of all relevant forcing agents. In our example in Figure 2, we assume that the model simulates an anthropogenic warming of 0.92°C in year 2020, i.e., an underestimation of 0.3°C compared to the observation-based estimate. Therefore, the remaining allowable warming is 0.68°C for the 1.5°C target, 1.18°C for the 2°C target and 2.18°C for the 3°C target. The approach for this option 2 is identical to option 1 except that the modeled temperature is used instead of the observed temperature.

Fig. 2: Schematic of the ‘absolute’ and ‘relative’ temperature targets. The schematic shows idealized temperature time series for the relative (red) and absolute (magenta) 1.5°C temperature target. In this idealized case, the model has ‘only’ warmed by 0.92°C until 2020 compared to the simulated average temperature from 1850 to 1900. For the relative target, the remained warming estimated from observations (0.28°C) is added to the realized warming in 2020, so that the relative temperature target is at 1.2°C. The absolute temperature target does not account for observations and defines the temperature target only with respect to the simulated average temperature from 1850 to 1900.

6. Executing the AERA algorithm

The AERA is implemented as an installable python module called *aera*. The module can be installed by cloning the official GitHub repository (<https://github.com/Jete90/AERA>) and then running “pip install .” inside the cloned directory (see README.md in the repository for more information).

Mainly two functions of the *aera* module are used by the end user:

- `aera.get_base_df()`: This function provides a template pandas.DataFrame (used as the data container for all time series) which is provided as an input parameter to `aera.get_adaptive_emissions()`.
- `aera.get_adaptive_emissions()`: This function calculates and returns near future fossil fuel emissions. As input, it requires several time series and constants as described below.

To simulate „AERA period 1” and „AERA period 2” (see section 4), new near future fossil fuel emissions must be calculated every five years (2025, 2030, ...) with the AERA. These emissions from the AERA are then provided to the model. To achieve this, each modeling group has to write a script that calls `aera.get_adaptive_emissions()` and then generates a CO₂ emission file for the ESM based on the annual emission output by the `aera.get_adaptive_emissions()` function.

To get started, first read through the documentation in the official GitHub repository (README.md) and then have a look at the example and template scripts.

- **Required time series input for the AERA at each stocktake/iteration**

The required input time series for the AERA is divided into two categories, (A) input from the respective ESM and (B) prescribed input as provided through this protocol. The time series are given to the function in the form of a pandas dataframe that is created within the script that calls the function. An example is attached to the code.

A) Input from the ESM

1. Annual timeseries of global mean surface temperature (GMST) from 1850 to the year of the stocktake [Kelvin]. This timeseries is used to derive the anthropogenic warming. You can use here also the global surface air temperature (globally averaged 2-m temperature). The trends are usually almost identical.

B) Prescribed input

1. Annual timeseries of global fossil fuel CO₂ emissions from 1850 to the year of the stocktake [Pg C yr⁻¹].

This timeseries is prescribed as defined in section 4 and hence extends itself adaptively over time after 2025. As the AERA yields the CO₂-fe emissions for the next five years, the CO₂ emissions are calculated as the difference of the AERA estimated CO₂-fe emissions and the prescribed CO₂-fe emissions derived from land use change and non-CO₂ radiative agents. It is used to estimate the TCRE and the REB.

2. Annual timeseries of CO₂-fe emissions from non-CO₂ radiative agents from 1850 to the year of the stocktake [Pg C yr⁻¹].

This time series is derived from the annual timeseries of the aggregated radiative forcing of all non-CO₂ radiative agents. This timeseries is used to estimate the TCRE and REB. The emissions corresponding to the timeseries from the RCP/SSP databases are provided. If your model can estimate the radiative forcing from all non-CO₂ radiative agents from 1850 to 2100, please contact us and we will calculate the corresponding CO₂-fe emissions for you. The latter is the preferred approach.

3. Annual timeseries of CO₂ emissions from land use and land cover change [Pg C yr⁻¹].

This time series is used to calculate the TCRE and REB. It should be calculated as the difference in carbon land-air flux between two concentration-driven simulations following historical+SSP1-2.6 CO₂ concentrations, one with land use change activated and without (see the LUMIP "hist-noLu" experiment, Lawrence et al. 2016, <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/9/2973/2016/>). The air-land and air-sea carbon flux have thus no influence on the atmospheric CO₂ concentrations. As the atmospheric CO₂ concentration is the same in both runs, the difference in land-air fluxes stems mainly from direct land use change emissions (we neglect in this way some feedbacks between land use CO₂ emissions and climate influencing land use emissions; Strassmann, K. M., F. Joos, G. Fischer, "Simulating effects of land use changes on carbon fluxes: past contributions to atmospheric CO₂ increases and future commitments due to losses of terrestrial sink capacity", *Tellus B*, 60/4, 583-603,2008). As land-use change CO₂ emissions can have large inter-annual variabilities, it is important that the time series of annual land use change CO₂ emissions is smoothed with a 21-yr running mean. If this is not possible, the CO₂ emissions from land use change calculated by the Bern3D-LPX model and smoothed with a 21-yr running mean can be used and are provided. The Bern3D-LPX CO₂ emissions from land use change are adjusted so that the historical CO₂ emissions from 1850 to 2020 are equal to the historical CO₂ emissions in the Global Carbon Budget. This adjustment was made because land Bern3D-LPX CO₂ emissions from land use change are relatively small compared to CO₂ emissions from land use change in other models.

C) Required parameters

- The target temperature described as a temperature anomaly (temp_target_rel). This must be set by the user.
- The year of the stocktake (year_x). This needs to be set to the year of the stocktake at each time the AERA is applied. It hence changes from 2025 to 2030 to 2035 to ... 2150.
- The year in which the historical simulation has started. This is usually 1850 but can be later, for example for the GFDL models in CMIP5.
- The AERA creates 3 output files with meta data that allows to recalculate the different steps of the AERA at each iteration. One file is a netcdf file and the other two are text files. All files are updated at each iteration and hence grow with time. The location of the files and the name of the netcdf file need to be precisely specified (/path/*nc). The text file names do not need a name as they are generated automatically based on the netcdf file as follows: /path/*nc.scalar.csv and /path/*nc.timeseries.csv.
- Choose between a relative temperature target based on the estimated remaining warming from observations (option 1) or an absolute temperature target based on the warming in the model (option 2).

7. Output of the AERA at each iteration

The AERA calculates the future CO₂-fe emissions time series for the years following the year of the stocktake. Within the algorithm, the CO₂-fe emissions from non-radiative forcing agents and from land use and land cover change are already subtracted. Therefore, the effective output is 'only' the fossil fuel CO₂ emissions per year. For the stocktake in 2025, for example, the CO₂ emissions from 2026 onwards are given as output.

To avoid model errors with boundary conditions (such as calculation CO₂ emissions in the model in December 2030 by making an interpolation of annually averaged prescribed emissions in 2030 and 2031), the CO₂ emissions file contains CO₂ emissions for an additional 5 years. 5 additional years were chosen arbitrarily here; please edit this file so that it can be read in by the respective ESM.

8. Simulations that should be delivered by all participants

To participate in the AERA inter-model comparison project, the participants are asked to perform the following mandatory simulations (Tier 1):

- Two simulations with a temperature target of 1.5°C ('absolute' and 'relative' temperature target) till 2100 but strongly encouraged to run to at least 2150. Any additional years are highly welcome, in particular if GSAT has not yet stabilized at the target.
- Two simulations with a temperature target of 2.0°C ('absolute' and 'relative' temperature target) till 2100 but strongly encouraged to run to at least 2150. Any additional years are highly welcome, in particular if GSAT has not yet stabilized at the target.

In addition, the following simulations are optional (Tier 2):

- One simulation with a temperature target of 3.0°C ('absolute' temperature target)
- One overshoot simulation: This simulation branches off from the simulation with an absolute temperature target of 2.0°C at the time when the temperature is at 2°C (visual inspection of the anthropogenic temperature). At the branch off time, the temperature target is set to 1.5°C and the simulation is run till 2200.

9. Necessary output from model simulations

From each simulation, the following output should be saved:

- AERA output and meta data files as described in section 6.
- Ascii or netcdf files of global annual mean absolute quantities (if not specified otherwise). Provide at least 5 significant digits for each variable.
 - Atmosphere:
 - tas: Near-Surface air temperature [K]
 - pr: Precipitation [mm yr⁻¹]
 - rsdt: TOA incident shortwave radiation [Wm⁻²]
 - rsut: TOA outgoing shortwave radiation [Wm⁻²]
 - rlut: TOA outgoing longwave radiation [Wm⁻²]
 - rtmt: Net downward radiative flux at top of model, Wm⁻²
 - co2: Mole fraction of CO₂ in air [ppm]
 - fco2fos: Carbon mass flux into atmosphere due to fossil fuel emissions of CO₂ [PgC yr⁻¹]

- Ocean:
 - tos: Sea surface temperature [K]
 - hfds: Downward heat flux at sea water surface, [W m^{-2}]
 - fgco2: Surface downward flux of total CO_2 [Pg C yr^{-1}]
 - intpp: Vertically integrated total primary (organic carbon) production by phytoplankton [PgC yr^{-1}]
 - o2: Dissolved oxygen concentration (globally integrated) [Pmol]
 - o2 (200m-600m): Dissolved oxygen concentration within the thermocline (averaged 200m-600m) [mmol m^{-3}]
 - ph (surface): Negative log of hydrogen ion concentration [-]
 - no3 (0-100m): Euphotic zone no3 concentration (averaged 0-100m) [mol m^{-3}]
 - epc100: Downward flux of particulate organic carbon at 100m [PgC yr^{-1}]
 - monthly area of Arctic sea ice (siconc > 0.15) [km^2]
 - monthly area of Antarctic sea ice (siconc > 0.15) [km^2]
- Land:
 - gpp: Carbon mass flux out of atmosphere due to gross primary production on land [PgC yr^{-1}]
 - npp: Carbon mass flux out of atmosphere due to net primary production on land [PgC yr^{-1}]
 - rh: Carbon mass flux into atmosphere due to heterotrophic respiration on land [PgC yr^{-1}]
 - nbp: Carbon mass flux out of atmosphere due to net biospheric production on land [PgC yr^{-1}]
 - cland: Total carbon in all terrestrial carbon pools [PgC]
 - fFireAll: Carbon mass flux into atmosphere due to CO_2 emissions from fire including all sources [PgC yr^{-1}]
 - cSoil: Carbon mass in model soil pool [PgC]
 - cVeg: Carbon mass in vegetation [PgC]
 - cLitter: Carbon mass in litter Pool [PgC]
 - cProduct: Carbon Mass in Products of Land-Use Change [PgC]
- The files should be named in the following way:

'variable_domain_model-name_non-ff-setup_temperature-target_target-type_ensemble-member_grid_start-end-dates.txt'

- **variable:** CMIP variables (e.g., 'tas')
- **domain:** CMIP domain (e.g., 'Amon')
- **model-name:** name of the ESM (e.g., 'MPI-ESM1-2-LR')
- **non-ff-setup:** name of the simulation that is used until 2014 for all forcing files and after 2015 for all files apart from CO_2 fossil fuel emissions (e.g., 'esm-ssp126')
- **temperature-target:** temperature target with two digits precision and the mentioned that it is reached adaptively (e.g., '150adapt' for a 1.5°C temperature target)
- **target-type:** absolute or relative temperature target type (e.g., 'rel' or 'abs')
- **ensemble-member:** following CMIP definitions (e.g., 'r1i1p1f1')
- **start-end-dates:** starting year and month as well as end year and month (e.g., '185001-210012')

An example filename would look like this: 'tas_Amon_MPI-ESM1-2-LR_esm-ssp126_150adapt_rel_r1i1p1f1_185001-210012.txt'

- We are generally interested in standard 2D/3D outputs as well, if possible in CMIP6 convention format. Please contact us so we can discuss the best way to transfer larger outputs and which variables.

- A text file in ascii describing the model, model resolution, model components, transient climate response, equilibrium climate sensitivity, transient climate response to cumulative carbon emissions as well as appropriate references. File name: Modelname_Modelversion_description.txt. Include contact address.

10. Provided files:

To execute the AERA algorithm, several files are provided:

- **Time series of annual mean CO₂ fossil fuel emissions [Pg C yr⁻¹]:** Emissions until 2020 are from the Global Carbon Project and emissions from 2021 to 2025 are estimated based on NDCs. The file contains constant emissions from 2026 onwards, but only to avoid computational problems. These numbers are not used. Please rename this file for each run as the emissions will be updated at each stocktake by the AERA and the file will be overwritten. Please also check if the emissions until 2014 are consistent with the prescribed emissions by the CMIP protocol. If not, please use the prescribed emissions until 2014 and replace them in this file accordingly (Filename: co2_ff_GCP_plus_NDC_v1.dat).
- **CO₂-fe emissions from non-CO₂ forcing agents [Pg C yr⁻¹]:** CO₂-fe emissions derived from the radiative forcing time series for non-CO₂ forcing agents (Filename: nonco2_emis_ssp126_v2.dat). If the radiative forcing from non-CO₂ forcing agents can be generated by your model as described above (point 6b), we will calculate the CO₂-fe emissions from non-CO₂ forcing agents for you. Please contact us in this case.
- **CO₂ emissions from land use change [Pg C yr⁻¹]:** CO₂ emissions derived from land use and land cover change by the Bern3D model and adjusted based on the past CO₂ emissions from land use change from the Global Carbon Budget (Filename: lu_emis_ssp126_bern3d_adj_GCB2020_v1.dat). If this can be generated by your model as described above (section 6b), please use that instead.

11. Model requirements:

The model must be able to compute the redistribution of anthropogenic carbon among the principal carbon reservoirs atmosphere, land biosphere, and ocean. Preferentially, the model simulates changes in climate in response to CO₂ radiative forcing and includes a representation of the relevant carbon cycle-climate feedbacks.

12. Contact:

For any question or update, please contact thomas.froelicher@unibe.ch and yona.silvy@unibe.ch.

13. Disclaimer:

It is a decision of the authors of this protocol whether submitted results are used or not used, e.g., in any forthcoming publication, product, or website. Co-authorship is offered in initial (peer-reviewed) publications when results are used. The results used in the publication as well as the output text files can be made publicly available on the web.